

3. Planning

📌 Introduction

On this page, you can find more information about the planning stage of the onboarding process. In general, the planning is carried out by the data holder or provider. At this stage, it is important to assess the scope of the onboarding at your institute, determine the required expertise, and create a project plan. You can find an example template bellow.

Steps 1-3 of the onboarding process

🧠 Understand the onboarding process

To create an onboarding plan, it is important to understand the process and its steps. You can refer to these pages for detailed information. If anything is unclear, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl.

🏢 Explore the situation at your institute

Another important step is to assess the available options at your institute for completing the onboarding process. For example, is there expertise in metadata? Is there a server where a FAIR Data Point (FDP) can be implemented? Is there an existing FDP at your institute that can be used? If you are unsure contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl and we can provide information on other onboarding projects within your institute or discipline.

Here are some questions that should be answered in this stage:

What?

- What data will be onboarded?
- What metadata schema is already in place?
- What security protocols exist at the data holder's/provider's institute, and how do they apply here?
- What infrastructural solutions are available at the institute, and how can the onboarding pipeline fit into them?
- What metadata can be shared? Are there parts of the metadata schema that cannot be shared due to ELSI concerns? (For more guidance on this topic, refer to this page: [Make sure you can publish your metadata](#))

How?

- How will the data be exposed to the National Health Data Catalogue?
- Will an institute-specific FAIR Data Point (FDP) be implemented?
- Can the metadata export be automated, or will it require manual entry?

Who?

- Who will be involved in the onboarding project from the data holder's/provider's side?
- Who will be responsible for maintaining the metadata?
- Who will be the primary contact person for the data holder/provider?
- Who else should be informed about the onboarding project (e.g., other data holders/providers, the board, the IT department)?

Next steps

If your plan for onboarding is complete. You can start with mapping your metadata to the Health-RI metadata standard: [4A Metadata mapping](#) and implementing an FDP [4B Exposing metadata](#) .

Questions?

If you have questions about the onboarding process or would like to learn more. Reach out to our Health-RI Servicedesk | Health-RI

 servicedesk@health-ri.nl